

NOVEL MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUES FOR OPTIMIZED 3D MULTIAXIAL ORTHOGONAL PREFORM

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ABSTRACT

Due to the existence of through-thickness Z-binder reinforcement, 3D woven preforms prevent delamination and crack propagation resulting in superior fracture toughness and impact damage tolerance properties. However, these 3D composites have lower in-plane mechanical properties, especially in an off-axis direction. To improve the in-plane mechanical properties and reduce the composite weight, preforms with different off-axis reinforcement are a present-day demand. This study presents the modification of traditional equipment and systematically developed new equipment to manufacture 3D preforms with different off-axis reinforcement and through-thickness binders. Manufactured samples with preform designs will be shown to demonstrate the innovative optimized and more versatile technology compared to conventional weaving. 3D composites manufactured with off-axis fibres are investigated for compaction and tensile behaviour and compared with standard 3D composites. The tensile behaviour showed the importance of the biased fibre when tested in the off-axis direction.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the past, composites were often designed with the “black aluminium” approach in mind when a quasi-isotropic layup was assumed to give almost the same properties as an aluminium alloy but provide a weight saving. Nowadays, the range of possible fibre architectures goes beyond unidirectional (UD) prepregs, layups are far more complex, and more design criteria than required stiffness properties need to be satisfied. Currently, numerical modelling frequently drives the design process of composites in terms of layup selection, stiffness and damage analysis. Modelling and optimization of prepreg layups showed that it is possible to achieve the required properties yet reduce components’ weight in comparison to traditional conservative designs.

Dry fibre preforms, especially near-net preforms such as 3D woven textiles, also can be optimized to achieve desirable properties. It was shown that optimization of the geometry of orthogonal 3D woven composites could help to achieve up to 20% weight-reduction [1], [2]. It was shown before that multi-axial 3D fibre preforms can be used to improve properties even further [3]. A numerical framework for optimization of 3D fibre preforms was created to drive the design of such multi-axial architectures in terms of their thickness, ply orientation etc. [3].

Currently, the Robotics group at the University of Manchester is working with three methods for enhanced 3D orthogonal preform manufacturing – modification of the conventional 2D looms, multi weft 3D looms and robotic tow placement (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Current 3D preforming toolbox: (a) 3D weaving Jacquard; (b) Multi weft 3D weaving; (C) Gantry Robot.

3D woven preforms can be manufactured by modifying the conventional weaving machine, i.e. looms with jacquard mounting for improved mechanical properties. By controlling the tow parameters, the preform properties can be tailored. It is also possible to produce various shapes of the preform with the modified loom.

Near-net-shape preforms can be directly manufactured in the newly developed multi weft insertion loom. Through thickness Z-binders can be added in any architecture such as orthogonal, angle interlock and layer to layer structures to meet specific applications.

An off-axis tow incorporating technique along with combined fibre placement and through-thickness binder yarns with tow steering has been designed to develop the machine. As a result, various types of multiaxial preforms with through-thickness reinforcement can be manufactured through this process.

An optimization framework has been developed utilizing the TexGen schema [3]–[5]. Such optimization can enable weight saving for a given set of performance requirements (Fig. 2). The optimization framework inspired the development of the machine, which can manufacture novel 3D multiaxial preforms.

Optimisation of laminates [6]

Meso-scale modelling

Figure 2: Preform optimization using modelling (adopted from [3, 6]).

2. METHODS

2.1. 3D multiaxial composite manufacturing

Robotics and Textile Composites group at the University of Manchester have developed several complex multiaxial 3D woven preforms with various lay-up configurations. To explore the mechanical responses of the developed preforms, two specific flat multiaxial 3D woven structures have been converted to composites. Lay-up configurations of these preforms are A – $90/0/90/0/90^\circ$ and B – $90/+45/0/-45/90^\circ$ (Fig. 3). The specification of preforms for each layer shown in Table 1.

Figure 3: Fibre lay-up configuration of the two 3D woven preforms: A – without the biased fibre and B – with the biased fibre in 45° direction.

Table 1 Specification of the 3D multiaxial preform

Layer no.	Layout direction (°)		Stuffer tow		Binder	
	A	B	Size	Density (tow/cm)	Size	Density (tow/cm)
1 (top)	90	90	24k X 1	2	6K	0.9
2	0	+45	24k X 2	4		
3	90	0	24k X 2	4		
4	0	-45	24k X 2	4		
5 (bottom)	90	90	24k X 1	2		

The composite laminates were made by using vacuum bag resin infusion process with Easy Composites IN-2 epoxy resin and AT- slow hardener at room temperature and cured for 30 hours; the laminates were cured. The Fibre volume fractions (FVF) were calculated by using the following equation.

$$V_f = nA / \rho T_f \quad (1)$$

where, V_f = Fibre volume fraction, n = the number of fabric layers, A = areal weight of the fabric, ρ = Density of the fibre, T_f = Thickness of the composite.

Sample A and Sample B have a volume fraction of 44% and 39%, respectively.

Samples were prepared to study the stuffer and binder tow paths. A Keyence VHX-5000 Optical microscope was used to study the internal geometry of multiaxial 3D woven preforms.

2.2. Preform compaction testing

Compaction tests of dry fibre preforms were carried out on a standard Instron machine. Square samples with nominal dimensions 80 mm×80 mm were put between two flat steel plates and compacted until the load reached 10kN. The fibre volume fraction of each sample was calculated based on the sample weight, its area and thickness of the preform monitored continuously.

Each of the dry fibre preforms was compacted several times to investigate potential differences between the first compaction cycle and subsequent cycles. One sample from each of the preforms was compacted at least 5 times while the rest of the samples were compacted 3 times.

2.3. Tensile testing

Tensile tests of the manufactured composite panels are carried out using an Instron Tensile Testing machine (Fig. 4) with 100kN load cell and video extensometer following the ASTM standard D3039. Tests were carried out both for the warp direction (0°) and off-axis (i.e. 45°) direction. A specimen size of $200\text{ mm} \times 25\text{ mm}$ was used for the samples and at least three samples were tested for each category. Due to the limitation in preform length, the sample length was reduced to 200mm instead of the standard 250mm.

Figure 4: Tensile test setting and testing the sample specimen.

3. DEVELOPMENTS AND RESULTS

3.1 Preform development

Modification to the yarn supply system in the conventional loom reduced the tow tension variation resulting in improved in-plane mechanical properties. Tow density was also varied to achieve the optimized preform [7].

Figure 5: Off Axis 3D weaving of T-Shape [8].

The near-net ultra-thick preform was developed by using the multi weft insertion loom. Angle-interlock binders were used to place off-axis fibres. The advantage of this technology is that selvages are protected from the fibre slip out from the structure. Also, fibre damage is reduced as the warps in multiple sheds are not moving up and down. A Near-net 3D woven T (Fig. 5) shape was manufactured using twenty two simultaneous weft insertions.

An off-axis angle was applied in the third preforming process for stuffer tows. Multiaxial 3D weaving preforms are made by this prototype machine (Fig. 6). It was developed by varying the off-axis angle. 36K tows for warp & weft and 6K tows were used in four layers (0° , 90° , $\pm 45^\circ$) to manufacture an orthogonal preform.

Figure 6: Multiaxial Orthogonal Preform

A cylindrical multiaxial preform (Fig. 7) was manufactured by using 6 layers of warp and weft tows (0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, $\pm 60^\circ$ and 90°) with an orthogonal binding pattern. Carbon fibre tow size used is 48K for making the layers and 6K for Z-binder, respectively.

Figure 7: Cylindrical Multiaxial Preform

Another development (Fig. 8) was to use multiaxial weaving, which gives the combination of biased fibre weaving with an orthogonal binding pattern for a much thicker preform. Stuffers can be inserted through any off-axis angle and binders in the orthogonal binding pattern are woven through for much higher thickness. The current development is a 70mm thick multiaxial 3D orthogonal preform, but the system can weave up to 300mm thickness.

Figure 8: Ultra-thick 3D multiaxial orthogonal preform

3.2 Geometrical structure of multiaxial 3D composites

Both the composites were studied with an optical microscope to explore their internal geometry. The optical images (Fig. 9), show the existence of almost non-crimped stuffer layer for the composite with $\pm 45^\circ$ Sample B fibres, whereas in $0/90^\circ$ Sample A without the stuffers are showing more crimp. As the non-crimp fibres carry more load than the crimped layers [9, 10], this combination of fibre layout in multiaxial 3D woven preforms opens the scope of improving the in-plane mechanical properties.

Figure 9: Cross-sectional images of the multiaxial composite. (a) weft-A, (b) warp-A, (c) weft-B, (d) warp-B.

3.3. Compaction behaviour

The results showed no significant difference between the preforms in compaction behaviour (Fig. 10). Repeated compaction testing showed that in the first compaction cycle, more force is required to compact the preform than in all other preforms (Fig. 11). It is related to the change in the geometry during the first compaction cycle when the fibre bundles distort (mainly flattening) but do not spring back.

Figure 10: Compaction behaviour of all tested preforms in the initial compaction cycle

Though no significant difference in the compaction behavior of the preforms with and without the biased fibres was found, these compaction data can be used to understand what fibre volume fraction is practically achievable in various liquid composites moulding processes.

Figure 11: Results of repeated compaction tests on one of the specimens

3.4. Tensile properties

In-plane tensile tests were carried out in the warp (0°) and off-axis (45°) direction for both of the samples. The elastic modulus of the composites was measured within a strain range of 0.1%-0.3%. Values of the tensile strength and tensile modulus were normalised for the meaningful comparison as the composites were varied in the volume fractions. Following equation (2) was used to calculate the normalised strength and modulus with an average volume fraction of 41.5%, which was calculated by using the FVF equation (1) for both the preforms.

$$\sigma(v_f) = \sigma(FVF_{av}/FVF) \quad (2)$$

where, $\sigma_n(v_f)$ = Normalised stress; σ = Ultimate tensile strength; FVF_{av} = Average fibre volume fraction of composites with tow density variation; FVF = Fibre volume fraction of the structure.

Values of the tensile strength and tensile modulus are presented in the bar chart for a clear comparison of the composite tensile behaviour.

The composite A, without the off-axis fibres, showed superior tensile properties in the warp direction both for stiffness and strength against the composite B. In the structure of multiaxial preform there is one layer less in the warp/ 0° direction which reduces the number of load bearing fibres in that composite. As a result, it has inferior tensile properties compared to the other composite (Fig. 12: a-b).

The tensile behaviour in the off-axis direction of the two composites is shown in Fig. 12 (c-d). In this case, the composite with the off-axis fibres showed higher tensile properties both for the stiffness and strength. The most interesting thing is the load carrying capability of the non-biased composite in this direction. As in this case, there is no continuous fibre that is gripped in the machine, i.e. no load bearing fibres, so it failed immediately resulting in very poor tensile strength and modulus. This problem is also reported by some previous researchers [11-12]. On the other hand, the off-axis fibres the biased composites help in load carrying resulting higher tensile properties compared to the other one in the off-axis direction.

Figure 12: Tensile properties of the multiaxial composites: (a) and (b) are the tensile modulus and strength in warp/0° direction and (c) and (d) are the tensile modulus and strength in off-axis/45° direction respectively.

4. CONCLUSION

3D orthogonal preforms with improved mechanical properties are a present-day demand. Conventional looms with process modification, multi weft 3D weaving technology and off-axis weaving technology with weft insertion and through-thickness binder can solve this issue.

Modification in warp and weft yarn supply system in a conventional 2D loom results in preforms with the least tow tension variation. And near net shaped preforms can be manufactured by using the multi weft insertion 3D loom. The novel preforming system can manufacture both flat and cylindrical multiaxial preforms. These newly developed preforms can be used for specific end uses that need off-axis loading with the reduction of weight and cost.

The physical and mechanical testing of the 3D composites with and without the biased fibres showed significant properties in off-axis direction. The geometrical structure of the multiaxial composite showed the existence of the layer with almost no crimp in their structure, which can contribute to the improvement of the in-plane mechanical properties.

The off-axis tensile testing results showed the important scope of these multiaxial 3D woven composites. Due to the existence of the $\pm 45^\circ$ fibres, in the off-axis directional tensile testing, the multiaxial composite showed much higher performance whereas the composite without the biased fibres exhibited lower modulus and strength. So the optimization in the preform layout gives the scope of improving the mechanical property of the 3D woven composites.

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